

Popular Article

Large roundworm of poultry: *Ascaridia galli*Dr. Suchita Kumari^{1*} and Dr. Anuruddha Singh Niranjana¹¹Assistant Professor, Department of Veterinary Parasitology
Apollo College of Veterinary Medicine, Jaipur, Rajasthan 302031**Abstract**

Large roundworm of poultry *Ascaridia galli* is the most common and pathogenic nematode, causes serious infections in young poultry and are very common in free ranging young birds. Diarrhoea, anaemia, unthriftiness, marked emaciation, retarded growth and decreased egg production are the important clinical signs. In heavy infection the worms lead to intestinal obstruction and rarely perforation of intestine leading to peritonitis and death. Regular deworming, treatment of the infected birds and adoption of good managerial practices are the important control measures.

Keywords: Poultry, *Ascaridia galli*, treatment and control

Introduction

Amongst all gastrointestinal nematodes, large roundworm of poultry *Ascaridia galli* is very common and prevalent throughout the world. *Ascaridia galli* causes serious infections in chickens of one to three months of age. It is commonly known as large roundworm of poultry, located in the small intestine of fowls, guinea fowls, turkey, goose and wild birds. Parasite comes under the Family Heterakidae of Order Ascaridida. Worms are thick and densely white in colour, eggs are oval, smooth shelled and comparatively smaller in size. *Ascaridia galii* has significant effect due to the direct life cycle of the parasite and ability to survive extreme environmental conditions (Sharma *et al.*, 2019).

Infection is most common in free ranging young birds while adults act as symptomless carriers. Infected birds will show diarrhoea, anaemia, unthriftiness, marked emaciation and retarded growth. Loss of appetite and body weight, ruffled feathers, drooped wings, retarded muscular and bone development, altered hormonal levels, anorexia, depression and increased mortality have reported in *Ascaridia galii* infection (Dahl *et al.*, 2002). *Ascaridia galii* infection has various effects on the performance, health, immune response, egg quality, decreased egg production of free-range layer bird (Sharma *et al.*, 2019). In heavy infection the worms cause intestinal obstruction and rarely perforation of intestine leading to peritonitis and death. Regular deworming, treatment of the infected birds and accommodation of good managerial practices are the important control measures.

Morphological characters of *Ascaridia galli*

- Worms are thick and densely white in colour. Measure upto 12cm.
- Both ends are pointed and cuticle is thick. Anterior end has three small lips.
- Oesophagus: posterior bulb is absent
- Tail of male has a large alae and a prominent precloacal sucker and 12 pairs of papillae.
- Spicules are unequal, the right one is long and cylinder and the left one is short and broad.
- Vulva lies behind the middle of the body.
- Eggs are oval, smooth shelled, comparatively smaller in size

Anterior end of *Ascaridia galli*

Posterior end of *Ascaridia galli*

Life cycle

- Life-cycle is direct. Earthworm may ingest egg and act as Transport host.
- Eggs embryonate in open and become infective with L2 stage in 10 or more days at optimum temperature.
- Infection of birds takes place on ingestion of infective eggs with feed or drinking water or earthworm.
- On ingestion of infective eggs, larvae hatched in the small intestine. The larvae live in the intestinal lumen for first 8 days post infection.
- Afterwards, majority of the larvae invade the intestinal mucosa and remain there upto 17 DPI (**histotrophic phase**).
- The larvae in their location reach third stage on 8 days post infection, and to L4 stage on 14-15 days post infection.
- The larvae then return to the intestinal lumen and become adults in 6-8 weeks.

Pathogenesis

- 1-3 months old chickens are most susceptible to *Ascaridia galli* infection.
- Previous exposure of infection makes the bird to more resistance.

- Some dietary deficiencies, like vitamin A, B and B12, minerals and proteins, predisposed to heavy infections.
- Massive larval invasion results in haemorrhagic enteritis and chicken become anaemic.

Clinical signs

- Diarrhoea, anaemia, unthriftiness, marked emaciation and retarded growth.
- Layer bird show decreased egg production.
- In heavy infection the worms lead to intestinal obstruction and rarely perforation of intestine leading to peritonitis and death.
- On postmortem examination, intestine seen haemorrhagic and large no. of adult worm.

Epidemiology

- Ascariidiosis is most common in free ranging young birds while adults act as symptomless carriers.
- Larvated eggs remain viable for three months under shade.
- Earthworm play important role in the prevalence of infection, act as a transport host.

Diagnosis

- Microscopical examination of faeces to identify oval, smooth shelled, small sized eggs.
- Necropsy finding- The adult large roundworms are seen in the small intestine.

Treatment

- Piperazine adipate or citrate is highly effective drug given @ 0.5 mg/kg b.wt. will eliminate 99-100% worm burden
- Phenothiazine @ 0.5-1 gm/bird is also very effective.
- Levamisole is also an effective drug given @ 30mg/kg or 300 ppm via feed
- Mebendazole should be given 60 ppm over 7 days

Control

- Treatment of all infected birds with suitable drugs
- Accommodation of good managerial practices such as
- Young and adult birds should be reared separately
- Regular cleaning of floor, Feeding and drinking water troughs
- Proper ventilation should be provided
- Regular deworming should be done with good anthelmintics at regular intervals
- Sterilization of the litters before the placing of each new batch of birds properly

Conclusion

The parasite *Ascaridia galli* has great significance in poultry industries in terms of production and economic losses. It has been associated with reduced health, immunity and egg production in layer birds and mortality in young birds due to heavy worms loads lead to intestinal obstruction. Hence young birds are most susceptible to parasite and have high mortality, they should be segregated from adults because they are symptomless carrier. Therefore, effective control of this parasite is necessarily required to minimise the production and economic losses to poultry industries.

Reference

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